

Bismuth tungstate inorganic ion exchanger — an absorbent for thin layer chromatography of organic acids

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A crystalline inorganic ion exchanger, bismuth tungstate has been found to be a useful absorbent for thin layer chromatographic separation of organic acids. The behavior of 19 organic acids has been studied on bismuth tungstate thin layers by utilizing several developing solvents of different nature. Efforts are also made for binary and ternary separations of bioanalytically important organic acids.

Because of rapidity, simplicity, low cost and excellent resolving power, silica gel thin layer chromatography has been used for the separation of various compounds¹. However, chromatographic behavior of organic acids on thin layers impregnated with inorganic ion exchangers has not been described in detail except a few publications². In this communication, we report the studies on the chromatographic behavior of some organic acids on bismuth tungstate impregnated silica gel thin layers.

Results and Discussion

The movement of some aliphatic, aromatic and substituted organic acids was observed in bismuth tungstate thin layers by using various polar, non-polar and mixed developing solvents. The results are presented in Table 1. The composition of the mobile phase is altered to achieve the desired separation. For comparison purpose, the movement of organic acids was also observed on unimpregnated (plain) silica gel thin layers under identical conditions. It was observed that spots of organic acids in most of the developing solvents are compact and well defined on impregnated thin layers in comparison of plain silica gel thin layers³. The movement of organic acids in most of the cases are found to be less than that observed on unimpregnated thin layers. This shows that bismuth tungstate thin layers serve as a good absorbent for organic acids and its immobilization on the thin layers retards the movement of various organic acids to different extent⁴. On un-impregnated silica gel layers, however, there is no such retardation force and hence comparatively a high movement of organic acids was observed than that on impregnated thin layers. Besides absorptivity, R_F value also depends on the kind of mobile phase solvent used. It is observed that in polar developing solvents including demineralized water most of the acidic spots spread over entire plate. On the other hand, in the non-polar devel-

oping systems such as carbon tetrachloride and benzene, no movement was observed. The failure of these solvents to effect the movement of organic acids may be attributed to the insolubility or sparing solubility of organic acids in these solvents. Thus these solvents can not be used for the separation of organic acids on bismuth tungstate thin layers.

Mixed developing systems such as acetone : water (1 : 1), ethyl acetate : formic acid : water (3 : 1 : 1), *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 2 : 3), ether : acetic acid : water (7 : 2 : 1), ethanol : ammonia : water (6 : 2 : 2), *n*-butanol : ammonia : water (5 : 2 : 3) and *n*-propanol : ammonia : water (6 : 2 : 2) have been proved to be useful. It has also been found that aliphatic hydroxy and amino acids show low movement on thin layers in almost all the developing solvents. Other acids, including aromatic acids have shown high movement in most of the solvents except basic one.

The separation on impregnated thin layers depends not only on partition, absorption and ion exchange mechanism but selectivity shown by the exchanger is also the significant advantage⁵. Thus bismuth tungstate thin layers, giving sharp, distinct and compact spots resulting cleaner separations, can be used for the separation of organic acids, present in the biological samples. Some of the important binary and ternary separations achieved are reported in Table 2.

Experimental

A stahl type TLC apparatus with universal applicator and thin layer 5 cm × 20 cm glass plate was used. Temperature controlled incubator was used for heating and activating plates. Sodium bismuthate (E. Merck) and sodium tungstate (B.D.H.) were used. Other chemicals, developing solvents and locating reagents were of A.R. grade. The spotting solutions were prepared either in ethanol or propanol. For visualization of spots, locating agents used were 1% ammonium vanadate in hot distilled water, 2% *p*-

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Note

Table 1. HR_F values of organic acids in different solvent systems on bismuth tungstate thin layers

Organic acid	S ₁	S ₂	S ₃ +S ₄	S ₅	S ₆	S ₇	S ₈	S ₉	S ₁₀	S ₁₁	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₁₄	S ₁₅
Oxalic acid	S	S	00	10	14	32	-	21	24	06	12	58	46	32
Succinic acid	S	S	00	6	18	28	24	66	67	68	74	42	34	29
Fumaric acid	S	S	00	00	00	20	28	68	76	74	86	38	34	26
Maleic acid	T	S	00	04	00	18	26	84	87	84	24	35	30	29
Citric acid	23	29	00	20	24	29	28	31	37	35	15	46	41	37
Tartaric acid	S	12	00	00	-	S	S	10	32	20	09	14	08	00
Adipic acid	18	24	00	26	34	36	38	88	84	76	-	37	30	24
Lactic acid	77	85	00	30	39	52	60	72	65	64	72	52	43	36
Amino acetic acid	S	S	00	16	24	26	24	62	65	26	-	05	00	00
Aspartic acid	S	S	00	10	16	20	19	49	57	31	-	12	08	00
Ascorbic acid	S	16	00	00	00	20	22	28	-	27	32	62	48	34
Benzoic acid	47	S	00	00	08	22	24	94	91	92	88	46	41	37
Phenyl acetic acid	88	96	00	10	14	28	81	88	92	89	90	72	62	50
Phthalic acid	S	S	00	0	06	26	20	68	73	72	92	48	37	31
Cinnamic acid	T	S	00	00	10	20	21	98	93	93	93	43	52	36
Salicylic acid	S	S	00	06	12	21	16	94	94	92	92	34	30	24
Gallic acid	S	S	00	00	18	20	32	69	67	52	55	-	22	10
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	S	S	00	00	00	18	36	94	95	84	91	28	19	08
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	S	S	00	00	00	16	21	98	94	92	93	26	16	-

S₁ = Demineralized water, S₂ = 0.1 M aqueous sodium chloride, S₃ = benzene, S₄ = carbon tetrachloride, S₅ = acetone, S₆ = ethanol, S₇ = ethanolic sodium chloride, S₈ = acetone : water (7 : 3), S₉ = acetic acid : water (8 : 2), S₁₀ = ethyl acetate : formic acid : water (3 : 1 : 1), S₁₁ = *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 2 : 3), S₁₂ = ether : acetic acid : water (7 : 1 : 1), S₁₃ = ethanol : ammonia : water (6 : 2 : 2), S₁₄ = *n*-butanol : ammonia : water (5 : 2 : 3), S₁₅ = *n*-propanol : ammonia : water (6 : 2 : 2).

S = Spread, T = tailing.

Table 2. Separations of organic acids on bismuth tungstate thin layers

Sl. no.	Separation of (HR _F)	From (HR _F)	Solvent
Binary separations :			
1.	Salicylic acid (16) or cinnamic acid (20) or phthalic acid (20)	Adipic acid (38), lactic acid (60), phenylacetic acid (81)	S ₈
2.	Oxalic acid (24) or citric acid (37) or lactic acid (65) or succinic acid (67)	Lactic acid (65), succinic acid (67), phthalic acid (73), fumaric acid (76), maleic acid (87), benzoic acid (91), phenyl acetic acid (92), cinnamic acid (93), salicylic acid (94)	S ₁₀
3.	Oxalic acid (6) or ascorbic acid (27) or citric acid (35)	Gallic acid (52), lactic acid (64), phthalic acid (72), adipic acid (76), maleic acid (84), benzoic acid (92)	S ₁₁
4.	Oxalic acid (12)	Ascorbic acid (32), gallic acid (55), lactic acid (72), succinic acid (74), fumaric acid (86), benzoic acid (88)	S ₁₂
5.	Lactic acid (72)	Salicylic acid (92)	S ₁₂

Ternary separations			
1	Succinic acid (16) or salicylic acid (16) or phthalic acid (20) or cinnamic acid (21)	Adipic acid (38) and lactic acid (60), gallic acid (38) and lactic acid (60), adipic acid (38) and phenylacetic acid (80)	S ₈
2	Oxalic acid (24) or tartaric acid (32) or citric acid (37)	Lactic acid (65) and benzoic acid (91), lactic acid (65) and cinnamic acid (93), succinic acid (67) and salicylic acid (94)	S ₁₀
3	Oxalic acid (6)	Ascorbic acid (27) and lactic acid (64), citric acid (27) and salicylic acid (92)	S ₁₁
4	Citric acid (35)	Succinic acid (68) and salicylic acid (89)	S ₁₁
5	Ascorbic acid (27)	Lactic acid (64) and salicylic acid (92)	S ₁₁
6	Oxalic acid (12)	Ascorbic acid (32) and gallic acid (55), ascorbic acid (32) and lactic acid (72)	S ₁₂
7	Maleic acid (24)	Lactic acid (72) and salicylic acid (92)	S ₁₂
8	Citric acid (15)	Gallic acid (55) and succinic acid (74), lactic acid (72) and phthalic acid (92)	S ₁₂

dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in acetic anhydride, 1% aqueous AgNO₃ with 5 ml NH₄OH, 2% aqueous anhydrous FeCl₃ with 1 ml conc. HCl, 2% ninhydrin solution in *n*-butanol, and 1% ethanolic bromophenol blue or bromocresol purple.

Bismuth tungstate was prepared by mixing, 0.1 M sodium tungstate and sodium bismuthate in the volume ratio of 1 : 1 as reported earlier⁵. The thin layer plates of 0.3 mm thickness were prepared by spreading a slurry of silica gel (50 g) and bismuth tungstate (25 g) of uniform grain size in distilled water (100 ml). The plates were activated for 4 h at 60 ± 1°. A set of similarly coated glass plates were prepared with a slurry of only silica gel for comparison purpose.

Approximately 0.04 ml of test solutions were spotted on the activated thin layer plates. The spots were allowed to air-dry and then the plates were subjected to development. For location of the spots the developed plates were first dried in air and then sprayed with suitable chromogenic reagent. The spots were marked immediately when they appeared on the chromatogram. The same procedure was followed for separations. The R_F values were calculated as usual.

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